

Dharmaraj K. Veer and Shivaji Sontakke, *Advancement and Challenges for College Libraries in IT Era* (New Delhi: Studera Press, 2018), Price: 1954.00, Pages: 385.

Reviewed by:

– **Sandeep Pathak**

Assistant Librarian, School of Liberal Studies
Pandit Deendayal Petroleum University
Gujarat

The edited book under review is divided into seven different sections examining the imperatives, process and status of development of library and information technology, especially the use of the e-Resources, library automation software, to make library an open source digital repository. Besides, the contributing authors have analyzed the role of library management and librarian during visit of The National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC).

The first part of the volume deals with the issue of application of Information Technology (IT) in libraries. The section scrutinizes how the information technology has become indispensable tools for accurate storage, processing, retrieval, and dissemination of information. As highlighted by K. Veeranjanyulu, all library professionals have to understand and adapt to the new roles in the promotion of digital information environment. Some authors have examined on the 'cloud computing' in greater details. The cloud computing is basically the practice of using online remote servers which is hosted on the Internet to store, manage, and process data, rather than a local server or a personal computer. U.D. Vikram discusses on the cloud computing and how security was the common concern about implementing it as it generally depend on networking. K. Suryawanshi explains in great details how the development and application of ICT has made significant improvements in library services that he broadly defines in terms of 4 Es - Economy, Ease, Extension and Efficiency). With the extensive use of ICT libraries now can extend services 24/7 worldwide in very cost effective manner. In addition, it has also changed the work professionalism of library professional and library services.

In the second section, authors have talked about the importance of collection development as it is integral to success of any library. B.S. Trimurtu while highlighting the rich legacy of India's publication tradition mentions in his research that *Darpan* was the first newspaper in Marathi language, started on 6 January 1832 by Balshastri Jambhekar and *Asiatic Researchers* was the first Indian journal published in 1788.

The third section of volume deals with 'e-Resources' available in every library in different forms like e-Journals, e-Books, e-Databases, e-Thesis, consortia, etc. The main purpose of e-Resources is to provide the latest information to the library users as per their requirement through the internet and from and in any corner of the world. As aptly highlighted by V.R. Morale and B.S. Murkate, the academic libraries prefer electronic resources to substitute print collection for best use and to address shortage of physical space. This also provides cost-effective sources when journal prices on the increase and unavailability of trained manpower. Undoubtedly, there are both advantages and disadvantages of e-Resources, which the librarian should be able to identify try maintain a balance.

Section four deals with 'library automation', which refers to the use of computers to increase efficiency of the library staff and provide new services to patrons. The main objectives of the library automation are: to increase processing efficiency, improve library service, avoid the duplication of work, and make library management efficient. This section describes the use of automation in library activities such as acquisition, cataloguing, and circulation. Especially in India, the commercial software packages like Sanjay, Libsys, Libman, Libra, Librarian, Memlib, E-Granthalaya, SOUL, etc. are popular.

Section five elaborates how librarians should work together with IT professionals to develop the knowledge management in twenty-first century. As reflected by G.P. Sambhaji, and G.N. Panchal, knowledge service should be enhanced by setting up virtual libraries for scientific research institutions, digitalized knowledge service and library resources. Librarians have to develop the resource collection and increase the reading materials for readers. Process and techniques for collection development are the major roles of librarians. The library management largely depend on the librarian and his/her professionalism in performance of duties including acquisition, cataloguing, digital repository, stock verification, and maintenance of library records.

The subsequent section discusses the use of library software and related issues. As present day libraries are gradually shifting from printed resources towards digital resources, digital library is fully automated information system

which saves precious time, strength and energy of the users. Authors mention some open source digital library software which can be used in digital libraries like DSpace, Greenstone, GNU E-Print, Ganesha, Libronix. Open source software have become very popular day by day and helped improving the library services and collection. Also these softwares do not cost the initial expenses like the commercial software. Some examples of open source software that have made the working environment smooth are: Koha, Fedora, Word Press, Open office, Ubuntu, Firefox, GIMP shop, etc. Open source phenomenon has attracted attention by digital revolution, economics of digital products, internet, new way of services. Though cost-effective open source software are available in market at ease but librarian should take utmost caution before selecting any for the library. V.M. Pawar mentions eleven criteria that are useful for selecting specific open source software.

The last part of the volume examines the role of librarian in the NAAC process. Undoubtedly, The Library and Information center of Higher Education institutions play a vital role in enhancing the quality of academic and research environment. Especially, authors in this section explain the Librarian's role is described regarding NAAC process that undertakes internal quality assessment and suggest how to develop a system for consistent and catalytic improvement for the overall performance of the institution. S.B. Deshmukh describes the role of library in developing quantity and quality collection on core and interdisciplinary subject. Also through collection of feedback about library and its services from the users it strives for constant improvement. For research consultancy and extension services library must have enough number of journals and convenient work space. For student support and progression the library has to provide user friendly services by efficient staff, orientation modules, exhibitions, guidelines and book bank services.

Overall, the volume is an important addition to the existing literature on the role of library in academic excellence and is a must read for the library management, the officials who are responsible for quality assurance in the university.